

Metadata	Test info	Test job details	
		Test parameters	
		Related research outcome	
	Material history and condition	As-manufactured material	
		As-tested material	
		Heat treatment	
		Microstructure	
		Chemical composition	
		NDT Results	
		Mechanical tests results	
	...		
	Test piece		
Measuring and test equipment	Test machine	Heating system	
		Test piece holder system	
		Data acquisition	
		...	
	Load-measuring system	Load sensor	
		Data acquisition	
	Laboratory conditions		
	Temperature-measuring system	Temperature sensor	
		Data acquisition	
		...	
	Extensometer system		
	Extension values	Contacting extensometer	
		Non-contacting extensometer	
...			
Elongation values and cross-sectional dimensions			
Data processing procedures			
Primary data	Test result	Values recorded at test start	
		Values recorded during test run	
		Values recorded after end of test	
		...	
Secondary data	Test result	Values recorded during test run	
		Strength values	
		Elongation values	
		Extension values	
		...	

Figure 1. Data schema structure for elevated temperature tensile test data of Ni-based superalloys. The image shows an excerpt of the full data schema. Specifically, it illustrates the four overarching levels of categorization, corresponding to columns “Category I” to “Category IV” of the attached XLSX file. The last granularity level (column “Entry”) is not displayed. Reproduced and adapted from Ávila Calderón et al. [2] under license CC BY 4.0 (Zenodo, 2024).